

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF THE UTILIZATION OF INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS IN TEACHING STATISTICS AMONG THE SCHOOLS IN BUTUAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the Teachers' Perception of the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics among Senior High Schools in Butuan City, focusing on random variables and probability distribution. Thirty-five teachers from eighteen selected schools participated during the SY 2017-2018, providing their perceptions through questionnaires based on the ADDIE model. Stratified random sampling was employed, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, weighted mean, standard deviation, and Chi-Square test. Results indicate that most teachers were between 20 to 30 years old, held bachelor's or master's degrees in mathematics, and had over 10 years of teaching experience. The analysis suggests that teachers highly value instructional materials, considering them essential for effective lesson delivery and emphasizing their relevance to the topic studied, despite limitations in availability. Demographic characteristics such as age, educational attainment, gender, and teaching experience did not significantly influence teachers' perceptions. This study underscores the importance of instructional materials in teaching statistics, irrespective of teacher demographics, emphasizing the need for their careful and strategic utilization in enhancing the teaching-learning process.

Keywords: *Instructional Material, Teaching Statistics, ADDIE Model.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a profession whereby the individuals who practice or intend to practice it help and facilitate others to acquire knowledge, competences or values. Teaching is a science where strategies and practices in a body of research has shown to be effective in enhancing learning; and at the same time an art, where teachers need to find the methods and strategies that work best for them and for the learners (Johnson, 2010).

Alvarado (2018) states that while teachers still frequently utilize the speak and chalk approach to impart mathematical information, it is no longer the norm in the classroom. Every teacher needs supplies and resources in order to be effective. Many studies suggest individuals can be classified according to different learning styles - audio learners, visual learners, verbal learners, etc., and teachers need to be equipped with resources to strategically achieve their objectives in class.

Instructional materials are the tools used in educational lessons, which includes active knowledge and evaluation. Basically, any resource a teacher uses to help them teach their students is an instructional material. Having a framework of the lesson is much effective when an application and integration of instructional materials (IMs) will be utilized in the teaching and learning process (Alvarado, 2018).

Instructional materials are tools that help to facilitate the teaching and learning process. Uses of instructional materials appeals to learners by creating interest goal that will help them achieve direct effort especially in the field of mathematics and statistics. Teacher's problem of goal is essentially one of arranging situation with instructional materials in which the learner will see goals he wants to achieve (Brown et. al. 2005).

In statistics, IMS has been introduced to foster deeper appreciation. Statistics as a branch of Mathematics with a wide variety of contents needs a healthy and well-developed knowledge and concepts for its contents. The K to 12 Curriculum Guide in statistics released by DepEd in 2013, one of its introductory content is the Random Variables and Probability Distributions.

Random Variables and Probability Distribution has an above average in difficulty and a major challenge for the teacher on how to deliver the information clearly. It is a must that the learner should demonstrate the understanding of key concepts of random variables and probability distributions and should be able to apply an appropriate random variable for a given real-life problem (such as in decision making and games of chance).

Lesson exemplars and instructional materials for this subject content will be a greater aid in achieving the competencies and desired skills leading to quality teaching and promoting globally acquainted learners. So to be an effective teacher, a statistics teacher in particular must know how to passionately craft and wholeheartedly devote their time in structuring lessons and producing materials for the benefits of learners (Alvarado, 2018).

The need for instructional materials in teaching statistics cannot be underestimated. The readiness and aptness of appropriate teaching modules are undeniably essential in strengthening fundamental quantitative and statistical skills. The non-availability of instructional materials that can easily convey the message of the lesson to the learners in the secondary education in the schools of Butuan City could greatly limit the effective methods and strategies that can be employed by the teachers.

Ensuring appropriateness of instructional materials being utilized in teaching statistics, a systematic approach known as the ADDIE model was utilized. Furthermore, this study highlights the evaluation phase of the ADDIE model wherein to gauge the teachers' perception of the utilization of instructional materials in teaching statistics among the selected schools in Butuan City.

Research Questions

This study would determine and assess the Teachers' Perception of the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics among the selected Schools in Butuan City. Specifically, it aims to seek the following questions:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the teachers teaching statistics?
2. What are the perceived scores of the Teachers' Perception on the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics?
3. Is there a significant difference in Teachers' Perception in relation to their demographic profile?
4. What are the manifestations and realization of the teachers on the significance of the instructional materials?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study

The study was conducted to different SHS Institutions within the City of Butuan. The list of schools is shown in table 1.

The respondents of the study were thirty – five (35) teachers among the Senior High Schools in Butuan City which are teaching Statistics during the SY 2017-2018, specifically Random Variables and Probability Distribution. In different schools, the researchers collected the following data:

Name of Schools	Number of Respondent/s
Agusan National High School	6
Alviola Integrated School	2
AMA Computer Learning Center	2
Ampayon National High School	1
Banza National High School	2
Basag Integrated School	1
BP Pueblos Senior High School	4
Butuan City Comprehensive High School	2
Butuan City School of Arts and Trades	1
Caraga State University-Senior High School	1
Father Urios Institute of Technology	3
Libertad National High School	1
Philippine Electronic, Communication and Information Technology	2
San Vicente National High School	1
Saint Joseph Institute of Technology	3
Taligaman National High School	2
Tungao National High School	1

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents

Sampling Design

The study used the stratified random sampling design in which the researchers' select respondents who are Senior High School teachers in Butuan City that are teaching Statistics during the SY 2017-2018 to get their perceptions towards the utilization of the instructional materials.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is delimited to and focused on Senior High School Statistics teachers among the selected schools in the City of Butuan. The research sample is composed of thirty-five (35) Statistics teachers teaching statistics and probability of eighteen schools in the city to determine the perception of the utilization of instructional material in teaching statistics specifically in the random variable and probability distribution.

The research data also was based on entirely from the questionnaires answered by the Statistic teachers based on their interaction with an instructional material provided to them by the researchers created through the ADDIE model.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting this study, the researchers wrote a letter asking permission to conduct a study to different institutions from the principals of selected SHS Schools within Butuan City.

The participants were given a brief instruction for them to get exact information about the questions from the proposed instructional material module on random variable and probability distribution and presented for their evaluation. Responses were tallied and tabulated for statistical analysis.

The research instrument used in gathering the data was the survey questionnaires adopted from the study of Ogbaji, D. (2017) entitled “Teachers’ Perception of the Utilization of Instructional Materials in Teaching Social Studies in Junior High Schools in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria”.

The questionnaire is made up of two sections, Part 1 is to seek information on the demographic characteristics of the teachers and Part 2 is the perception of the utilization of instructional material.

Statistical Treatment

After the data gathered were compiled, sorted out, organized, and tabulated, the data is subjected to the statistical treatment to facilitate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation.

The following statistical tools or test procedures were utilized:

1. Frequency count and percentages was used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents through pie charts and bar graph.
2. Weighted Mean (Average) and Standard Deviation was used to determine the perception of the respondents on the utilization of instructional material.
3. Chi-Square test was used to address the null hypothesis and determine the significant association of the teachers’ demographic profile and their perceptions.

RESULTS

Problem 1. What are the demographic profiles of the teachers teaching statistics?

Figure 1: Distribution of the Respondents Age

Figure 2: Distribution of Respondents' Educational Background by Gender

Figure 3: Distribution of Respondents by Number of Years Teaching

Problem 2. What are the perceived scores of the Teachers' Perception of the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics?

Perception on the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics	Average Score	Standard Deviation	Remarks
The use of instructional materials makes lesson delivery easy.	4.74	0.44	Highly Agree
The effectiveness of instructional materials is dependent on their relevance to the topic under study.	4.37	0.60	Highly Agree

The teachers judiciously utilize instructional materials even when they are available in minimal quantity.	4.06	0.59	Agree
Instructional materials are in short supply in secondary schools in Butuan City.	3.91	0.92	Agree
The lack of utilization of instructional material is the reason for not actualization the topic on Random Variables and Probability Objectives.	3.89	0.47	Agree
Instructional materials on Statistics, particularly on Random Variables and Probability Distribution is lacking in Butuan City.	3.71	0.79	Agree
Community resources are widely used in Butuan City.	3.40	0.81	Agree
The topic of Random Variables and Probability Distribution can be taught effectively even without instructional material.	2.77	1.14	Either Agree or Disagree
Improvisation is not necessary if the instructional material is unavailable.	2.74	1.07	Either Agree or Disagree
Teachers find sometimes difficult to the use of an instructional material in the teaching process.	2.74	1.01	Either Agree or Disagree

Table 2. Perception on the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics

Problem 3. Is there a significant difference in Teachers' Perception in relation to their demographic profile?

Variables	Test Statistic	p-value	Remarks
Age	8.805	0.117	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.341	0.733	Not Significant
Gender	-0.936	0.349	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	1.642	0.440	Not Significant

Table3. significant difference in Teachers' Perception in relation to their demographic profile

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 reveals the distribution of our respondents by age. The figure shows that majority of our teacher-respondents were 20 to 30 years old. 23% of our respondents were 30 to 40 years old. Also, 8% of our teachers were 40 to 50 years old while 6% were 50 years old and above.

Several investigators have found a curvilinear age function, with productivity beginning at a relatively low rate in the late 20s, peaking around 40, and declining thereafter (Homer, Rushton, & Vernon, 1986). With respect to teaching effectiveness, investigators have provided less definitive results. Recent reviewers have concluded that either no relation or a negative relation exists between age and quality of teaching (Blackburn & Lawrence, 1986).

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the teacher-respondents based on their educational background by gender. The figure displays that most of our teachers teaching statistics in Butuan City were holding a bachelor's degree majoring in mathematics and almost half of that were master's degree holders in mathematics teaching.

Di Dio et al. (1996) suggest that there are different values and self-construal's present in males and females. However, the results showed that there were no significant differences between males and females in terms of how they judge the usefulness of instructional methods in teaching statistics.

Findings related to teachers' academic degrees (e.g., bachelors or masters, etc.) are inconclusive. Some studies showed positive effects of advanced degrees (Betts, Zau, & Rice, 2003), while others showed negative effects (Ehrenberg & Brewer, 1994). Teacher Education in the Subject Matter of Teaching (in-field preparation) This characteristic is related to the subject-matter knowledge teachers acquire during their formal studies and preservice teacher education courses. The evidence gained from different studies is contradictory. Several studies show a positive relationship between teachers' qualifications and their impact on student achievement findings (Goldhaber & Brewer, 2000), while others have less unequivocal results. Monk and King (1994) find both positive and negative effects of teachers' in-field preparation on student achievement. Goldhaber and Brewer (2000) find a positive relationship in mathematics, but none in science. Also, Rowan, Chiang, and Miller (1997) report a positive relationship between student achievement and teachers' majoring in mathematics. Monk (1994), however, finds that having a major in mathematics has no effect and a significant negative effect of teachers with more coursework in physical science. The results of the study showed that there was no significant relationship between the teacher's educational attainment to their perception on the utilization of instructional materials in statistics.

Figure 3 displays the distribution of the respondents' number of years of teaching experience. The figure reveals that most of our respondents have more than 10 years of experience with the percentage of 43%. 39% of the teachers have less than 5 years of teaching experience while 18% have 5 to 10 years of experience.

Studies on the effect of teacher experience on student learning have found a positive relationship between teacher effectiveness and their years of experience, but not always a sign or an entirely linear one (Murnane & Phillips, 1981). Studies suggest that while inexperienced teachers are less effective than more senior teachers, the benefits of experience appear to level off after a few years (Rivkin, Hanushek, & Kain, 2000). The relationship between teacher experience and student achievement is difficult to interpret since this variable is highly affected by market conditions or motivation to work during the child-rearing period. Harris and Sass (2007) point to a selection bias that can affect the validity of drawing conclusions about the effect of teacher's years of experience. The results show that there is no significant relationship between the teacher's number of years in teaching experience to their perception in utilizing instructional materials.

Table 2 shows the scores of the teachers on their Perception on the Utilization of Instructional Material in Teaching Statistics. The table shows that the respondents highly agree that the use of instructional materials makes lesson delivery easy with a mean of 4.74 and the effectiveness of instructional materials is dependent on their relevance to the topic under study with a mean of 4.37.

Kay (2008), Instructional materials stimulate the students' desire to learn. It assists learning process by making assimilation and memorization of materials easy. Also, it helps to hold attention, includes greater acquisition and, as well as objectives which may be inaccessible to many students. Teaching at any level requires that students be exposed to some form of simulation. Ikerionwu, (2000), refers to instructional materials as objects or devices that help the teacher to make learning meaningful to the learners. Instructional materials, which are educational inputs, are of vital importance to the teaching of any subject in the school curriculum. Wales (1975), opined that the use of instructional materials would make discovered facts glued firmly to the memory of students. A teacher who makes use of appropriate instructional materials to supplement his teaching will help enhance student's innovative and creative thinking as well as help them become enthusiastic, Ekwueme, and Igwe (2001). Instructional materials make teaching and learning more effective. They can be manipulated, seen, heard or talked about as instruments which facilitate such activity. Esu, Erukoha, and Umoren (2004) stated that instructional materials are necessary ingredients in the development of any curriculum.

Instructional materials facilitate teaching and learning activities and consequently, the attainment of the lesson objectives. However, this depends on the adequacy and appropriateness of materials so selected. This in effect, means that learning resources are not selected haphazardly (Jiya, 1993). Indeed instructional materials to be used should be carefully selected by the teachers. The obvious facts remain is that people remember those they have seen, touched and even played with. The primary task of teaching is to facilitate effective learning and understanding of the content materials (Shoji, 2005). Instructional materials which appeal to all learners' understanding of the language phenomena should be encouraged for use in our schools.

Furthermore, the teachers agreed on the careful utilization of instructional materials even when they are available in minimal quantity (4.06) and instructional materials are in short supply in secondary schools in Butuan City (3.91).

According to Mitzal (in Azeb, 1998), when there is lack of materials that appear geographically to the understanding of the pupil, teaching can be a challenge indeed. In light of this statement Tirusew (1998) also describes that for effective teaching-learning to take place, the classroom must be adequately organized and conducive enough. The crux of educational quality among others heavily relies upon the environmental (both internal and external) materials whenever theoretical issues are presented in classrooms for students, it is practically proven that students get the most out of them when they are supported by teaching materials (Houlok, 1990). The writer argued that a classroom should encompass teaching materials like textbooks.

In addition, the teachers concur that the lack of utilization of instructional material is the reason for the non-actualization of the topic on Random Variables and Probability Objectives with a mean of 3.89 and that the Instructional materials on Statistics, particularly on Random Variables and Probability Distribution is lacking in Butuan City with a mean of 3.71.

The use of instructional materials can enhance the learning achievement. Cronbach (2009) states the important elements of behavior that provides the base for learning theory situation which consists of all the objects, persons, and symbols in the learning environment.

According to Adeniyi (2000), the use of teaching aids and materials are to communicate move permanently and the information is retained when supplemented with aid certainly instructional materials which carefully selected and skillfully used. It also makes learning more effective, therefore it becomes necessary to investigate how instructional materials serve as tools in the teaching and learning situation.

Moreover, the teachers also agree that the community resources, like the library, are widely used in Butuan City (3.40).

Hao-Ren (2012) suggests that school and public libraries must have cooperation in order to deliver the materials needed to implement the curriculum design. Playing as the local gateway to knowledge, the public library is essential for lifelong learning, independent decision-making and cultural development of the individual and social groups. The public library aims a providing all kinds of knowledge, information, and services readily and equally available to her patrons. Collections of the public library must cover broad subjects and be suitable for patrons of all age groups. The Public library should endeavor to reduce the digital divide by offering Internet services for those who cannot access the Internet at home (UNESCO, 1994).

Esu (1995) asserted that the main aim of instructional materials in the teaching of Mathematics is to increase the effectiveness of teaching mathematics as a means of preparing learners for future responsibilities as adults. Textbooks and other learning materials may influence teachers' beliefs about mathematics (Collopy, 2003).

Mathematics manipulative-based instructional techniques are approaches that include opportunities for students to physically interact with the objects to learn target information (Carbonneau & Marley, 2012).

Table 3 shows the table of significance in the perceptions scores on teaching statistics among the demographic profiles of the teachers. The table reveals that for all profiles of the teachers, none has a significant difference in their perceptions. Age (0.117), Highest Educational Attainment (0.733), Gender (0.349) and Teaching Experience (0.440) show no correspondence on their perceptions. The remarks denote that regardless of the status and background of the teachers, their perceptions on the importance and relevance of the instructional materials in teaching senior high school statistics with emphasis on random variables do not significantly differ.

In a study on the impact of teachers' qualification on students' performance, Colfalter, Ladd, and Vidgor (2006) found that a significant difference exists in the mean performance of students in schools staffed with qualified teachers and those schools staffed with unqualified teachers. Adeniji (2004) supported this finding to a great extent that teachers' qualification has a potent relationship with students' achievement. Ukewe (1999) observed that many students draw inspiration from competent and good teachers who are essentially qualified. This means that educational training influences job performance and also acts as a reliable indicator of the type of work one should look for. Iheanacho (2002) argued that teachers with higher education qualification are more effective than those with lower qualification and that skilled teachers with some additional skills are more productive than the unskilled.

Problem 4. What are the manifestations and realization of the teachers on the significance of the instructional materials?

Moreover, some teachers have realizations on the use of instructional materials; the following were some constructive comments from the respondents:

“Instructional materials should be appropriate to the topic.”

This statement emphasizes that teachers must choose instructional materials that are appropriate to the topic and the teachers must be creative in making it.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

There are instructional materials that can be use in different ways, it only depends on the topic because if we use instructional materials that is not suit to the topic, it is still useless.

Thank you!

“There are instructional materials that can be use(d) in different ways, it only depends on the topic because if we use instructional materials that (are) not suit(ed) to the topic, it (IMs) is still useless.”

One of the respondents clearly emphasizes the importance but according to the comment, it will only depend on the topic.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

Instructional materials should be relevant to the topic discussed at hand. Effectiveness of IM is not dependent on the quality of its content rather it is about the quality of delivery of its content. The module is very applicable and useful for the teachers, it enhances students' understanding and increase the teachers' effectiveness in teaching the lesson.

Thank you!

“Instructional material should be relevant to the topic discussed at hand. (The) effectiveness of IM is not dependent on the quality of its content rather it is about the quality of delivery of its content. The module is very applicable and useful for the teachers. It enhances student’s understanding and increase(s) the teachers’ effectiveness in teaching the lesson.”

One of the respondents clearly emphasizes that in teaching specific subject matter in Probability and Statistics like Random Variable and Probability Distribution, instructional materials should be relevant to the topic and must be used effectively utilized to have a desirable result. Modules will also help the teachers to make the teaching-learning process effective.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

Instructional Materials will vary to the type of students in the class. It must be use to cater all the multiple intelligences and diverse students.

Thank you!

“Instructional materials will vary to the type of students in the class. It must be used to cater the multiple intelligence and diverse students”

This statement wants to convey to the researchers that Instructional materials must cater different learners inside the classroom and the teacher must use the instructional materials effectively.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

Instructional Materials are beneficial to both teachers and learners. Teachers could find it easy to impart the topic to be discussed, on the other hand learners can easily understand the topic if instructional material are included in the teaching process.

This instructional material in teaching Random Variable can really help learners grasp and understand the topic under much effort of the teacher.

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The respondent wants to emphasize that using Instructional materials in teaching statistics and probability helps both the teachers and the learners to make the teaching-learning process more meaningful. Instructional materials could help the learners not just to understand the topic but also to use this knowledge in real life situations.

Akanbi (1988) defined instructional materials as materials designed to enrich the teaching and learning processes and hence contribute to better learning. Leohard (1999), conceived instructional materials as “a wide range of materials and devices, designed to provide realistic imagery and substitute experiences in order to enrich curricular experiences of many kinds”. From the aforementioned meanings of instructional materials, the best way of helping pupils to learn is to bring them face to face with the world which education intends to introduce to them (Mkpa, 1989). He stressed further that

one way this can be attained is by using real objects in real life situations for instruction. Where real life situation is not possible, the alternative is for the teacher to use representations of real-life situations. These representations are materials, devices, and techniques that help the teacher to make a realistic approach to his job. Whether real or substitutes, these representations have a common goal. They help the teacher to convey the intended message effectively and meaningfully to the learners so that the learners receive, understand, retain and apply the experience gained to reach overall educational goals.

Some teachers have also their manifestations on the use of instructional materials; the following were some constructive comments from the respondents:

“For us, Senior High (School) Teachers in Statistics and Probability, the instructional materials should be the same (with) what the curriculum guide is or even not the same total(ly) but almost (the same).”

The comment suggested that IMs should be the same with the curriculum guide provided by the Dep-Ed or even have the same idea and thought of the curriculum.

“Instructional materials should be made by the teacher and not being supplied to the schools because the teacher knows his/her students the most”

The respondent suggests that the teacher must be the designer of their own instructional materials. Teachers know what should be done inside the classroom and what should be the appropriate IMs that should be used.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

Instructional materials should be provided by the government to facilitate easy learning process for the students and less time and effort in the preparation of classroom instructions and lessons the burden in the part of the teacher with respect to financial problem.

Thank you!

“Instructional materials should be provided by the Government to facilitate (the) easy learning process for the students and less time and effort in the preparation of classroom instructions and lessens the burden in part of the teacher with respect to financial problems.”

This comment suggests that the Government must support the teachers in providing instructional materials to the teachers and give them an opportunity to have seminars to improve their skills in preparing effective IMs.

Suggestions for the Instructional materials:

ON TEACHING RANDOM VARIABLES AND PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION WE SHOULD RELATE THE EXAMPLES ON THE STUDENTS EXPERIENCES TO GET THEIR ATTENTION AND USING INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS WILL MAKE THE DISCUSSION EASIER AND TIME SUFFICIENT.

Thank you!

“On teaching Random Variables and Probability Distribution, we should relate the examples on(of) the students(‘) experiences to get their attention and using instructional materials will make the discussion easier and time sufficient.”

This suggests that IMs help the teaching and learning effective and time sufficient if we will relate the IMs to the students’ real-life experiences.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are the conclusion drawn the profiles of the teachers has no significant difference in their perceptions. The Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Gender and Teaching Experience show no correspondence on their perceptions. The remarks denote that regardless of the status and background of the teachers, their perceptions on the importance and relevance of the instructional materials in teaching senior high school statistics with emphasis on random variables do not significantly differ.

Recommendations

On the basis of the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations have been made:

1. The Instructional materials should be made appropriately for all topic in statistics.
2. Community resources such as public libraries should be enriched with instructional materials in line with the Dep-Ed Curriculum.
3. Public libraries and school libraries must collaborate in order to ensure readiness and appropriateness of the instructional materials that teachers can use in teaching statistics.
4. An appeal or request must be made to Dep-Ed in order to coordinate with schools offering SHS in order to provide training and seminars to SHS teachers to enhance their skills in creating effective instructional materials in teaching Statistics and Probability that will make the teaching-learning process more meaningful.
5. A criteria must be established to evaluate Instructional Materials. Such may be used by the teachers themselves to judge the materials they use in their lessons.
6. Guidelines must be released for a procedure of regular evaluation or update of IMs to ensure relevance and aid the achievement of the objective which is to apply the lesson in real-life situations.
7. The researcher proposed an instructional material in Random Variable and Probability Distribution which might be useful in the teaching-learning process. The researcher followed the K to 12 curriculum guide for Grade XI.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The following are necessary to guarantee that research is carried out ethically and honestly.

Informed consent. In order to conduct a study, the head of the school will be written a letter by the researcher to gain permission. The participants will be informed particularly about all the aims and objectives of the research.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The participants are given orientation before answering the survey questionnaire in pursuance of RA 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal and/or sensitive information collected and disclosed by this survey shall be used solely for purposes of the study.

Conflict of Interest. The researchers are disclosing any financial or personal conflicts of interest that could potentially bias the results or their interpretation.

Fairness and Equity. Researchers make sure that everyone is treated equally, respectfully, and without prejudice based on factors like ethnicity, gender, or socioeconomic position.

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